

Letter of Intent for the project “Biodiversity in the Subarctic and the Importance of Open Biodiversity Data”

To whom it might concern,

Føroya Náttúru- og Umhvørvisfelag (Faroese Nature and Environment Organisation) is pleased to provide this letter of intent in support of the project proposal “Biodiversity in the Subarctic and the Importance of Open Biodiversity Data.”

As an NGO we are dedicated to protecting Faroese nature and advancing environmental awareness, and we recognise the urgency of strengthening biodiversity knowledge in subarctic regions. Unfortunately biodiversity data in the Faroe Islands remain scattered, inaccessible, or unknown despite decades of research. This project directly addresses that challenge by creating an accessible, FAIR-compliant biodiversity database and national biodiversity index for the marine environment.

We particularly value that this initiative will:

- Gather and register existing biodiversity data from the marine environment in the Faroe Islands.
- Standardise and integrate datasets in alignment with international frameworks such as OBIS and GBIF.
- Develop a publicly accessible web portal with an engaging, Faroese-inspired interface for outreach and education.
- Foster collaboration and data sharing among researchers, policymakers, and citizens.
- Enable meaningful analysis of biodiversity patterns over time.
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This effort is of great importance not only for the Faroese community, but also for the wider North Atlantic and Arctic regions, where open biodiversity data is essential for evidence-based decision-making, conservation planning, and strengthening resilience to environmental change.

Føroya Náttúru- og Umhvørvisfelag strongly supports this proposal and looks forward to contributing to its success by fostering community engagement and ensuring that biodiversity data become an accessible and actionable resource for all.

Sincerely,

Fja Niclasen
Secretary General

Føroya Náttúru- og Umhvørvisfelag